

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE INFLUENCE OF ETHNOCENTRISM ON CONSUMER LOYALTY IN LOCALLY MADE FURNITURE (CASE STUDY ON SOLO FURNITURE MARKET CONSUMERS, INDONESIA)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10581755>

Abstract

A number of studies have identified that ethnocentric consumers prefer to buy domestically produced products compared to foreign products. However, this research focuses on countries with large economies, therefore its application in developing countries is still rare. On the other hand, this research is focused on products, and that is the reason why research on hedonic services is also scarce. The aim of this research is to identify ethnocentrism attitudes in consumer loyalty to buy local furniture products at the Solo Furniture Market by applying the variables ethnocentrism, patriotism, collectivism and individualism. The aim of this research is to provide a solution to develop and increase consumer loyalty to buy locally made furniture compared to buying from other countries.

Keywords: ethnocentrism, patriotism, collectivism and individualism

Introduction

The furniture industry as a subsector of the agro-industry contributes 1.30% to non-oil and gas GDP in 2022. Apart from that, in the same year, the furniture industry had an export performance worth 2.47 billion USD. "In the midst of the threat of a global recession which previously caused the growth of the furniture industry to experience contraction, in the first quarter of 2023 the growth of the furniture industry has shown an increase compared to the second quarter of 2022 (Ministry of Industry, 2022). Previous studies have explained that consumers often choose to buy products made in their home country rather than products made abroad. This may be due to the influence that the place of origin of the product plays on consumers' desire to purchase (Papadopoulos & Heslop, 1993). Ethnocentrism is one of the variables studied to better understand these behavioural patterns. In the field of consumption, ethnocentrism allows us to identify the degree of influence of the origin group on local consumers in relation to their purchasing habits as well as their perception of the quality of foreign products (S. Sharma et al., 1994; Shimp & Sharma, 1987).

Due to the availability of natural resources in the country, the national furniture industry is able to compete on the global stage because of its innovative products. This shows that this industry is a sector that has the potential to develop. The Ministry of Industry noted that the export value of furniture products (HS 9401-

9403) in 2020 reached USD 1.91 billion, an increase of 7.6% from 2019 which reached USD 1.77 billion. The largest export destination countries for Indonesian furniture in 2020 include the United States, Japan, the Netherlands, Belgium and Germany (Ministry of Industry, 2022).

Previous research considers that consumer loyalty allows for preferences towards one particular service provider; This gives rise to commitment to buy again from them, social and emotional bonding, and reduced sensitivity to service prices (Hwang & Wen, 2009). Ethnocentric consumers tend to develop loyalty towards national brands (Ogba & Tan, 2009; Rowley, 2005).

Ethnocentrism is a traditional concept that influences purchasing decisions regarding foreign goods and services. In addition, according to (Fernández-Ferrín et al., 2015) the concept of customer ethnocentrism implies an increase in local purchases and a decrease in interest in foreign products. Ethnocentrism is represented by an overall attitude that focuses on morality in purchasing foreign-made and domestic-made products and services (Ma et al., 2020). For example, research conducted by (Han & Guo, 2018) argues that customers' ethnocentric values has a positive effect on the intention to buy domestic products. Since (Shimp & Sharma, 1987) initiated research on customer ethnocentrism, various studies have separately explored behavioural preferences, cognitive biases, and affective

reactions, ethnocentrism factors, and brand factors such as brand loyalty. In other words, previous research focuses on the one-dimensional structure of customer ethnocentrism (Balabanis & Siamagka, 2017; Fernández-Ferrín et al., 2015; Narang, 2016). However, researchers say that various studies are needed regarding the multidimensional structure of customer ethnocentrism (Bizumic, 2019; Boukamba et al., 2021). Therefore, the current study attempts to fill this gap. Furthermore, this research aims to expand research on the application of customer ethnocentrism attitudes based on individualism, patriotism and collectivism by using a multidimensional structure of customer ethnocentrism to measure customer loyalty in the furniture industry in the Solo Furniture Market.

Literature Review

1. Ethnocentrism

Working from a sociological perspective, Camacho et al., (2020; Thomas, (1907) define the concept of ethnocentrism as the perception that individuals have of the group they belong to as well as their assessment of that group compared to other groups. The reason is that the perception held by their own group becomes a reference. According to Lee et al., (2020) ethnocentrism can be interpreted as a lack of acceptance of cultural diversity and intolerance towards outside groups which tends to give rise to negative prejudice towards other cultural groups therefore ethnocentrism is included in xenophobia. This ethnocentrism produces a phenomenon called consumer ethnocentrism in American consumers. The North is characterized by the level of appreciation shown for products from their own country of origin. This appreciation for the place of origin is based on concerns about the possible loss of economic interests in the country itself due to high imports. This leads to the intention not to buy foreign products (Shimp & Sharma, 1987).

In relation to this topic Luque-Martínez et al., (2000) consider that ethnocentric consumers have a high tendency to express biased judgments and overvalue local products. This tendency allows them to emphasize the positive aspects of these products and downplay or downplay the benefits of imported products. Therefore, ethnocentric consumers will consider the values of their ethnic group or country as a symbol of pride and a representation of national unity. Keeping these concepts in mind, Sharma [38] concluded that consumer ethnocentrism represents a favorable inclination towards anything related to the group to which one belongs (in-group) and a bias towards anything related to groups to which one does not belong. within it (the in-group). outside group). This results in attitudes with three distinct dimensions: affective reactions, cognitive reactions, and behavior. This behavior is reflected in the beliefs held by consumers regarding purchasing services offered by foreign companies.

2. Patriotism

P. Sharma (2015) defines patriotism as a person's dedication, through feelings of love and devotion, to their home country. For Louis J. Mihalyi (1984) this also functions as a defense mechanism when dealing with third parties. Balabanis & Siamagka (2017) define patriotism as a feeling of strong attachment and loyalty

towards one's own country but not creating hostility towards other countries. (Durvasula & Lyonski (2009) consider that patriotism is closely related to the sense of pride a person feels towards their own country and this is reflected in their favoritism towards people, their way of acting, and their own country's values. Therefore, patriotism is related to perceptions held by individuals regarding their country of origin and everything related to it. For (Blank & Schmidt, 2003) there is a difference between patriotism and nationalism. The former tends to associate positive values such as the level of people's commitment to their country of origin, while nationalism has negative implications because it increases the glorification of the country of origin above all else. Therefore, the handling must be different.

Consumer patriotism has a significant influence on the intention to purchase domestic products compared to purchasing foreign products. Thereafter, when high levels of patriotism are encountered, people, cultures, and products whose origins differ from those of the consumer may be rejected. Highly patriotic consumers support national producers because it assumes an obligation and expression of loyalty towards the country of origin. (Puncheva-Michelotti & Michelotti, 2014) patriotism ultimately provides a competitive advantage to local products and strengthens the sensation of national identity that individuals feel through purchasing these products. Other research confirms the positive relationship that exists between patriotism and consumer ethnocentrism, (P. Sharma, 2015) even in the service sector, (de Ruyter et al., 1998). Because of the relationship explained above, hypothesis 1 is as follows:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Patriotism has a positive influence on ethnocentrism attitudes

3. Individualism and Collectivism

Values related to individualism and collectivism exist in everyone. For most people, the tendency toward collectivism first develops in primary groups such as the family. Later, other, more individualistic tendencies developed. People who develop more individualistic values show strong characteristics of independence and separateness towards their own group, whereas people with collectivist tendencies show strong characteristics of family integration and interdependence towards their own group. Given these facts, in collectivist cultures, both the behaviour of its members as individuals and the behaviour of groups are guided by the group; in contrast, in individualistic cultures, the behaviour of individuals in groups is driven by the individuals themselves. It is for this reason that when conflict arises in individualistic cultures between group goals and individual goals, differences are resolved in the interests of the individual, whereas in collectivist cultures, differences are resolved in the interests of the group (Hui & Triandis, 1986; Kapoor et al., 1995; Triandis et al. al., 1990). In collectivist cultures, it is possible to identify how group members tend to subordinate their personal goals to those of a particular group; instead, it is possible to observe how members of individualistic cultures use groups only as a means to achieve their personal goals (Hui & Triandis, 1986).

Hofstede et al., (2010) define culture as a collective phenomenon where people live in the same social environment and where culture is learned and not inherited; The authors adopted five dimensions as their descriptors: power distance, individualism versus collectivism, masculinity versus femininity, uncertainty avoidance, and long-term orientation. Referring to the dimension of individualism versus collectivism, Colombia is one of the countries with the lowest level of individualism in Latin America. Thus, it can be concluded that this is a collectivist society where strong relationships are maintained between group members and dependence on the group is considered important to achieve its goals. Despite this, Colombian society is very focused on achieving success through competition. Even though it is a collective society, the implication of this focus is that competition arises with members of other groups or even with other social classes and also the granting of status (Hofstede et al., 2010)]. With previous research conducted by de Ruyter et al. (1998); P. Sharma (2015); van Birgelen et al. (2004) in our mind, we consider it possible that people from collectivist societies show strong ethnocentric tendencies whereas people from individualist societies do not show strong tendencies. Because of the relationship explained above, hypothesis 2 and hypothesis 2 are as follows:

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Collectivism has a positive influence on ethnocentrism attitudes

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Individualism has a positive influence on ethnocentrism attitudes

4. Loyalty

Customer loyalty can be defined as the perceived superiority of the product purchased by consumers, giving rise to social bonds and emotional attachment (Ogba & Tan, 2009), for this reason loyalty is demonstrated both through repeat purchases and in consumers'

attitudes towards the product, thus determining the level of commitment to the brand, (Beerli & Martin, 2004). For Rowley (2005) this is the way in which loyalty results in lower sensitivity to price fluctuations and represents less cost to acquire new clients and as a result, greater profitability. For (Bowen & Chen, 2001) However, the benefits of loyalty are demonstrated by better attitudes towards the company, commitment to purchasing the product, and making recommendations to others. (East et al., 2005) consider that in the service sector, loyalty is a deep-rooted commitment from consumers, which results in consistent future repeat purchases of a service, despite various influences designed to change behavior.

Hwang & Wen (2009) client loyalty results in positive direct marketing through word of mouth, where consumers easily identify their preferences for certain service providers. Meanwhile, Schlesinger et al. (2017) identified the benefits of loyalty as a tendency that persists after consumers stop using a service. Therefore, loyalty refers to the period during which consumers actively use a service and the period after service use, thereby contributing to the enhancement and promotion of the image and reputation of the service they receive.

As noted by Zeithaml et al. (1996) ethnocentric consumers generally value their loyalty to national brands, thereby reflecting their intention to remain within their own group, negatively impacting loyalty to foreign products (Abosag & Farah (2014)]. Makanyeza (2015) emphasized that loyalty results in repeat purchases, the result of consumer commitment to preferred brands. Because of the relationship explained above, hypothesis 4 is as follows:

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Ethnocentrism has a positive influence on loyalty attitudes

Research Framework

Picture 1. Research Framework

Research Method

A quantitative study based on a structured questionnaire was used to verify the hypotheses proposed by the model, the survey method is adopted in this study to collect data. Our target respondents were consumers from Solo Furniture Market, which is the largest furniture market. The data was collected through a field survey in Solo city, Indonesia in October-November 2023.

A total of 300 interviewees responded to the questionnaires. All returned responses were carefully examined. After checking all the questionnaires, we excluded 22 responses, either due to the missing data or because the answers to all questions were the same. Convenience sampling was used, and 280 valid questionnaires were obtained. The principal characteristics of the study with regards to the demographic profile of the survey participants and the distribution of the sample according to

the classification variables: 66,8% were men and 33.2% were women. The age range of survey participants was 1.6% between 18 and 25 years of age, 4.6% between 26 and 36 years of age, 12.8% between 36 and 45 years of age, 56.4% between 46 and 55 years of age with 12.8% of survey participants older than 55 years of age. In relation to education, 41% were secondary school educated, 44.9% had university studies, and 12.1% postgraduate studies.

Analysis and Results

The collected data was analyzed in two steps. The measuring instrument was validated in the first step, followed by a structural model assessment using Smart PLS. This technique was chosen since the usage of PLS is gaining popularity in a variety of marketing studies and on a global scale. It provides for both formative and reflecting structures. Palacios-Florencio (2018) identified formative indicators in image construction, which we evaluated in our study. When analyzing these constructions, the weights factor must be considered rather than the factor loadings. The authors acknowledged the possibility of multicollinearity among formative indicators. PLS modeling aims to predict dependent variables with the highest R2 ratio for explained variance.

This allowed parameter estimates to be based on the ability to minimize residual endogenous variance. In this scenario, PLS allows for better adaptation to predictive research when compared to other techniques. The decision to utilize PLS is also justified by the study's predictive nature, as well as the fact that the image construct is treated as a construct with formative signs.

An examination was conducted using Fornell's (1981) to confirm discriminant validity, criteria and the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT). According to Fornell's (1981) criteria, the square root of each variable's AVE should be bigger than its correlations with the other variables in the model. As can be observed in Table 1 all the square roots of the AVE of each construct are greater than the correlation with any other construct in the mode. As seen in Table 2, all of the square roots of each construct's AVE are bigger than the correlation with any other construct in the model (Fornell, 1981). The (HTMT) ratio considers 0.90 to be a suitable maximum cutoff value. As seen in Table 1, all values of the (HTMT) ratio are less than 0.9.

Table 1.

Discriminant validity criteria according to Fornell					
	Patriotism	Individualism	Collectivism	Ethnocentrism	Loyalty
Patriotism	0.709				
Individualism	0.347	0.823			
Collectivism	0.244	0.406	0.851		
Ethnocentrism	0.412	0.314	0.373	0.876	
Loyalty	0.408	0.122	0.029	0.159	0.925

Table 2.

Discriminant Validity, HTMT Ratio				
	Patriotism	Individualism	Collectivism	Ethnocentrism
Patriotism				
Individualism	0.492			
Collectivism	0.342	0.728		
Ethnocentrism	0.453	0.457	0.513	
Loyalty	0.480	0.198	0.158	0.278

After assessing the measurement instrument's psychometric properties, the structural model was analyzed using PLS using the same criteria used to calculate the significance of the parameters. The R2 acquired via bootstrapping was the initial step in determining the structural model's predictive capacity. This indicated how much variance in a construct could be explained by the construct's predictor variables in the model.

Table 3.

Results of the Structural Equations Model (SEM)						
Hypothesis	Relationship	β	t	p-Value	Result	
H1	Patriotism → Ethnocentrism	0.315	6.387	0.000	Accepted	
H2	Individualism → Ethnocentrism	0.100	1.799	0.038	Accepted	
H3	Collectivism → Ethnocentrism	0.254	4.799	0.000	Accepted	
H4	Ethnocentrism → Loyalty	0.612	16.265	0.000	Accepted	

The positive link that exists between patriotism and ethnocentrism is evidenced by the results obtained. As such, the Hypothesis H1 is confirmed. Due to this and according to the significance of the relationship previously stated, it can be confirmed that this construct wields a positive and significant on ethnocentrism ($\beta=0.315$; $p < 0.000$). In the same way, collectivism also

has a positive and significant influence on ethnocentrism. This leads to the confirmation of Hypothesis H2 ($\beta= 0.100$; $p < 0.036$). A relationship is observed between individualism and ethnocentrism, allowing us to confirm Hypothesis H3. Considering the significance of this result, we can conclude that individualism has a positive and statistically significant effect on SET ($\beta=$

0.254; $p < 0.000$). According to the results obtained, a positive and statistically significant relationship exists between ethnocentrism and loyalty towards local furniture ($\beta = 0.612$; $p < 0.000$), thus accepting Hypothesis 4.

Discussion

This study intends to contribute to the research into the concept of ethnocentrism related to local furniture. Similar studies have, to date, focused on developed countries. According to Sheth (2015), the rise of emerging markets has a significant impact on marketing practice and theory, requiring a shift from a local to a global mindset. Therefore, studying emerging markets is becoming increasingly important. It suggests inviting future academics to conduct additional research in these markets every day. Under this perspective, this job has contributed to the limited literature on ethnocentrism in hedonic services, as well as local furniture management developed in the context of an emerging market such as Indonesia, resulting in contributions that allow local furniture to perform strategies for excellent development in these emerging markets. The findings corroborate, first, a positive and significant association between patriotic sentiment and collectivism and ethnocentrism, as proven in prior research. This study also supports the concept that these components increase degrees of ethnocentrism. According to the findings of this study, ethnocentrism influences local furniture loyalty in hedonic services, and so improving all experiential and hedonic components of service consumption is a meaningful way to increase the effects of a country's ethnocentrism. In any event, we advocate a prior analysis of the ethnocentric character of a country's inhabitants as a vital variable for designing local furniture strategy.

References:

1. Abosag, I., & Farah, M. F. (2014). The influence of religiously motivated consumer boycotts on brand image, loyalty and product judgment. *European Journal of Marketing*, 48(11–12), 2262–2283. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-12-2013-0737/FULL/XML>
2. Balabanis, G., & Siamagka, N.-T. (2017). Inconsistencies in the behavioural effects of consumer ethnocentrism. *International Marketing Review*, 34(2), 166–182. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMR-03-2015-0057>
3. Beerli, A., & Martín, J. D. (2004). Factors influencing destination image. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 31(3), 657–681. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2004.01.010>
4. Bizumic, B. (2019). Effects of the dimensions of ethnocentrism on consumer ethnocentrism. *International Marketing Review*, 36(5), 748–770. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMR-04-2018-0147>
5. Blank, T., & Schmidt, P. (2003). National Identity in a United Germany: Nationalism or Patriotism? An Empirical Test With Representative Data. *Political Psychology*, 24(2), 289–312. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0162-895X.00329>
6. Boukamba, H. K., Oi, T., & Sano, K. (2021). A Generalized Approach to Tourist Ethnocentrism (GATE): Analysis of the GenE Scale for Application in Tourism Research. *Journal of Travel Research*, 60(1), 65–85. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287519895128>
7. Bowen, J. T., & Chen, S. L. (2001). The relationship between customer loyalty and customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 13(5), 213–217. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596110110395893/FULL/XML>
8. Camacho, L. J., Salazar-Concha, C., & Ramírez-Correa, P. (2020). The Influence of Xenocentrism on Purchase Intentions of the Consumer: The Mediating Role of Product Attitudes. *Sustainability*, 12(4), 1647. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041647>
9. de Ruyter, K., van Birgelen, M., & Wetzels, M. (1998). Consumer ethnocentrism in international services marketing. *International Business Review*, 7(2), 185–202. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-5931\(98\)00005-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-5931(98)00005-5)
10. Durvasula, S., & Lysonski, S. (2009). How offshore outsourcing is perceived: Why do some consumers feel more threatened? *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 21(1), 17–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08961530802125225>
11. East, R., Gendall, P., Hammond, K., & Lomax, W. (2005). Consumer Loyalty: Singular, Additive or Interactive? [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1441-3582\(05\)70074-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1441-3582(05)70074-4)
12. Fernández-Ferrín, P., Bande-Vilela, B., Klein, J. G., & del Río-Araújo, M. L. (2015). Consumer ethnocentrism and consumer animosity: antecedents and consequences. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 10(1), 73–88. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-11-2011-0102>
13. Han, C. M., & Guo, C. (2018). How Consumer Ethnocentrism (CET), Ethnocentric Marketing, and Consumer Individualism Affect Ethnocentric Behavior in China. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 31(5), 324–338. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08911762.2018.1437649>
14. Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G. J., & Minkov, M. (2010). *Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind* (Third). McGraw Hill Professional. https://books.google.co.id/books/about/Cultures_and_Organizations_Software_of_t.html?id=o4OqTgV3V00C&redir_esc=y
15. Hui, C. H., & Triandis, H. C. (1986). *Individualism-Collectivism* (Vol. 17, Issue 2). Sage Publications: Thousand Oaks, CA. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022002186017002006>
16. Hwang, J., & Wen, L. (2009). The effect of perceived fairness toward hotel overbooking and compensation practices on customer loyalty. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 21(6), 659–675. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596110910975945>
17. Kapoor, S., Wolfe, A., & Blue, J. (1995). Universal values structure and individualism — collectivism: A U.S. test. *Communication Research Reports*, 12(1), 112–123. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08824099509362046>
18. Kemenperin. (2022). *Kemenperin Upayakan Industri Furnitur Terus Berekspansi*. Kemenperin.

<https://www.kemenperin.go.id/artikel/24050/Kemenperin-Upayakan-Industri-Furnitur-Terus-Berekspansi>

19. Lee, Y. L., Jung, M., Nathan, R. J., & Chung, J.-E. (2020). Cross-National Study on the Perception of the Korean Wave and Cultural Hybridity in Indonesia and Malaysia Using Discourse on Social Media. *Sustainability*, 12(15), 6072. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12156072>

20. Louis J. Mihalyi. (1984). ETHNOCENTRISM VS. NATIONALISM: ORIGIN AND FUNDAMENTAL ASPECTS OF A MAJOR PROBLEM FOR THE FUTURE on JSTOR. *Humboldt Journal of Social Relations*, 12(1). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23262698>

21. Luque-Martínez, T., Ibáñez-Zapata, J., & del Barrio-García, S. (2000). Consumer ethnocentrism measurement - An assessment of the reliability and validity of the CETSCALE in Spain. *European Journal of Marketing*, 34(11/12), 1353-1374. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090560010348498>

22. Ma, J., Yang, J., & Yoo, B. (2020). The moderating role of personal cultural values on consumer ethnocentrism in developing countries: The case of Brazil and Russia. *Journal of Business Research*, 108, 375-389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.12.031>

23. Makanyeza, C. (2015). Consumer Awareness, Ethnocentrism and Loyalty: An Integrative Model. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 27(2), 167-183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08961530.2014.980927>

24. Narang, R. (2016). Understanding purchase intention towards Chinese products: Role of ethnocentrism, animosity, status and self-esteem. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 32, 253-261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2016.05.010>

25. Ogba, I., & Tan, Z. (2009). Exploring the impact of brand image on customer loyalty and commitment in China. *Journal of Technology Management in China*, 4(2), 132-144. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17468770910964993>

26. Papadopoulos, N. G. (Nicolas G.), & Heslop, Louise. (1993). Product-country images : impact and role in international marketing. *International Business Press*. https://books.google.com/books/about/Product_country_Images.html?hl=es&id=z8PE4zEFSGkC

27. Puncheva-Michelotti, P., & Michelotti, M. (2014). The new face of corporate patriotism does being

“local” matter to stakeholders? *Journal of Business Strategy*, 35(4), 3-10. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBS-10-2013-0090/FULL/XML>

28. Rowley, J. (2005). The four Cs of customer loyalty. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 23(6), 574-581. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02634500510624138>

29. Schlesinger, W., Cervera, A., & Pérez-Cabañero, C. (2017). Sticking with your university: the importance of satisfaction, trust, image, and shared values. *Studies in Higher Education*, 42(12), 2178-2194. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2015.1136613>

30. Sharma, P. (2015). Consumer ethnocentrism: Reconceptualization and cross-cultural validation. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 46(3), 381-389. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jibs.2014.42>

31. Sharma, S., Shimp, T. A., & Shin, J. (1994). Consumer Ethnocentrism: A Test of Antecedents and Moderators. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 23(1), 26-37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070395231004>

32. Shimp, T. A., & Sharma, S. (1987). Consumer Ethnocentrism: Construction and Validation of the CETSCALE. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 24(3), 280-289. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224378702400304>

33. Thomas, W. I. (1907). *Folkways. A Study of the Sociological Importance of Usages, Manners, Customs, Mores, and Morals*. By William Graham Sumner, Professor of Political and Social Science in Yale University. (Boston: Ginn and Company. 1907. Pp. v, 692.). *The American Historical Review*, 13(1), 116-117. <https://doi.org/10.1086/AHR/13.1.116>

34. Triandis, H. C., McCusker, C., & Hui, C. H. (1990). Multimethod probes of individualism and collectivism. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 59(5), 1006-1020. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.59.5.1006>

35. van Birgelen, M., de Ruyter, K., & Wetzels, M. (2004). THE ROLE OF SOCIALLY DESIRABLE RESPONDING IN INTERNATIONAL SERVICES RESEARCH. *Advances in International Marketing*, 15, 75-91. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-7979\(04\)15004-7/FULL/XML](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-7979(04)15004-7/FULL/XML)

36. Zeithaml, V. A., Berry, L. L., & Parasuraman, A. (1996). The Behavioral Consequences of Service Quality. *Journal of Marketing*, 60(2), 31-46. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224299606000203>